

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D6.5 – Data Collection and Pilot Assessments

I

WP6 iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies

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Executive summary

This document represents the assessment of the iHelp approaches by showing the proposed data collecting processing and modelling flow. This workflow's final purpose is to provide to the clinicians a better insight of the Pancreatic Cancer disease.

There are five pilot studies within the iHelp designed to help test and validate the personalized solution developed in this project by providing different types of data which is useful within the various aspects/scenarios of disease prevention.

The five pilots involved in this project, provide the input data needed for the iHelp technical partners to analyse and compile smart models that can help with predicting this type of disease.

Upon the completion of the 1st iteration of this report on D6.5 ("Data Collection and Pilot Assessments I"), adjustments and improvements will be made and will be reflected in the 2nd iteration of this deliverable, i.e., D6.6 ("Data Collection and Pilot Assessments II").

This document contains the description of data collection processes and procedures and the instruments used to evaluate these processes. It also describes the evaluation mechanisms of pilot studies.

The data collection instruments section presents an overview of what the data collection strategy is for each pilot, how data will be formatted and distributed and what is the methodology for data ingestion into the iHelp platform from each pilot's perspective.

Pilots will present details about the measuring of the data quality by describing the evaluation instruments for data collection and assessment measures. Pilots will present details about the data quality and quantity and will describe how the data flow is managed.

To ensure proper data flow and smooth ingestion of the data from the pilots to the iHelp platform, partners have identified potential risks that could appear, and the solutions that alleviate the impact of these potential issues.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of this deliverable

The scope of this deliverable is to describe the overall data and research designs of the pilot studies. It comprises three parts: mechanisms, evaluation measures and pilot execution risk assessment.

The mechanisms refer to the processes of how pilot studies will be conducted and the description of the corresponding preliminary on-site data processing, storage and data ingestion pipeline into iHelp platform.

The document presents a detailed evaluation of the data collection instruments, the assessment measures taken by the pilots as well as risks assessments and proposed mitigation actions with regards to the data collection process.

1.2 Connections with other deliverables

In relation to the two types of data collected by each pilot, namely primary data and secondary data, as described in D2.1 (“State of the art and requirements analysis I”), D3.3 (“Primary data capture and ingestion I”) and D3.5 (“Secondary data capture and interoperability I”) this document represents an extension of these deliverables, in terms of pilots’ evaluation and data quality assurance, by answering to questions like: “How to make sure that the ingested data is controlled and of good quality?”.

What is more, D6.1 (“Coordination of pilot scenarios for personalized healthcare – early risk identification, prevention and intervention measures I”) presented the methodology for data collection implemented by each pilot, the tools that enable the data acquiring and how the data will be merged with other pilots, while this document contains the data collection instruments and data information. In addition, the present deliverable details any changes considering planning and requirements of pilot studies and data, as compared to deliverable D2.2 (“State of the art and requirements analysis II”).

Moreover, in the present deliverable, information on data acquisition and data processing performed at clinical sites, before the ingestion into the iHelp platform, while D3.7 (“Standardisation and Quality Assurance of Heterogenous Data I”) presented the design and initial specification of the iHelp Standardization and Quality Assurance Mechanism for data processes after ingestion, that will consist of three core sub-components: Data Cleaner, Data Qualifier and the Data Harmonizer which will ensure that the data flowing into iHelp respects the imposed standards. The D3.7 (“Standardisation and Quality Assurance of Heterogenous Data I”) also contained dictionary and descriptions of the sample datasets provided.

In the iHelp project, two main models of data are considered: the EHR (Electronic Health Record) and the HHR (Holistic Health Record) model. In this deliverable a Data Mapping strategy between the clinical data and the HHR model is presented, while deliverable D3.1 (“Data Modelling and Integrated Health Records: Design and open specification I”) provided information of how the data inserted into iHelp will be structured and mapped in the HHR model. Further information and details on the pilots’ provided data can be found in Section 3 of D2.1 (“State of the art and requirements analysis I”) deliverable which describes the various datasets that each pilot will provide to the iHelp platform, along with the data requirements necessary for the secondary data collection during the project. The risk assessment included here in Section 5 refers to

the data collection process, while the risks related to the start of the pilots are included in D6.3 (“Pilot setup and implementation of digital trials I”).

Ethical information regarding pilot studies execution is already included in D1.9 (“Ethical Issues Related to the Involvement of Humans in iHelp”), D1.10 (“Ethical Issues Related to the Protection of Personal Data”) and D6.3 (“Pilot setup and implementation of digital trials I”) deliverables. The D6.3 (“Pilot setup and implementation of digital trials I”) deliverable provides information of the status of the pilot studies ethical approval. While D1.9 (“Ethical Issues Related to the Involvement of Humans in iHelp”) provides an overview of the pilot activities in the iHelp project that specifically address human involvement. In addition, it describes the relevant ethical compliance criteria defined by the EC (European Commission) and the specific steps are defined to ensure compliance with relevant procedures governing people's ethical involvement in health research projects. In addition, the D1.10 (“Ethical Issues Related to the Protection of Personal Data”) deliverable analyzes the ethical, legal, and regulatory issues related to the protection of personal data that may arise during the iHelp project, while providing an overview of the existing literature. The integrated use, management, and processing of data in the project and its solutions make ethical, legal, socio-economic, cultural and data protection issues a cornerstone of this project.

1.3 Structure

The document contains three main topics: data collection instruments which is detailed in Section 2, evaluation instruments and assessment measures treated in Section 3 and 4, and finally risk assessment of the data collection which is handled in Section 5.

This report is structured in the following sections: Section 1 presents an overview of this deliverable content and structure. Section 2 offers information on the data collection processes and procedures for primary and secondary data. Moreover, Section 3 considers the evaluation instruments for data collection, Section 4 introduces pilot assessment measures, and Section 5 details the risk assessment procedures. Finally, Section 6 concludes the document providing an overall conclusion and overview, while also discussing next steps.

2 Data collection instruments: processes and procedures

This section is composed out of three parts: data collection strategy and details, data format and distributions and data ingestion process and methodology.

The purpose is to detail the way data is handled by each pilot before entering the iHelp platform.

- **Data collection strategy and details**

Primary data collection represents the process of acquiring the data from patients or external sources.

This subsection describes in detail how will the primary data (the variables) be collected and stored, along with the corresponding frequency of data collection and the strategy performed for cancer risk assessment.

- **Data format and distributions**

This subsection offers information on the data format and its corresponding required distribution. It also provides information on the pilot studies changes considering planning and requirements as compared to deliverable D2.2 (“State of the art and requirements analysis II”).

- **Data ingestion process and methodology**

Data ingestion refers to the process of introducing or transferring the data to the iHelp platform, after the data collection process. The data coming from clinical databases, storage units, FTP servers or APIs is to be transferred to the platform Gateway, which is further detailed in D3.3 (“Primary data capture and ingestion I”). The process starts from preliminary data processing, followed by the data ingestion process with its corresponding frequency of ingestion and possible estimated delays between collection and ingestion.

Data ingestion frequency differs from data collection since the data can be inserted into the platform at a later stage and not during or immediately after data acquisition.

2.1 Primary data

Primary data refers to recorded data from a cohort of patients and usually comes from stored Electronic Health Records.

2.1.1 Pilot #1 – UNIMAN

2.1.1.1 Data collection strategy and details

Primary data collection for UNIMAN pilot constitutes the process for acquiring data from participants in the community. UNIMAN will provide primary data that will include data derived from the Risk Estimation for Lifestyle Enhancement Combined Trial (REFLECT) cancer risk assessment (L., A., T., + 17) (L., U., C., + 17) and the genetic biomarkers (SNPs - Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms) from the blood sample. This data will be in Comma-Separated Value (CSV) format with password protection. The data will be kept at the UNIMAN assigned premise and university-managed computer. Data will be stored on the P-drive which is secure storage for personal files and documents on the University’s network. The university-managed computer is encrypted and maintained by IT Services. Furthermore, as part of the University’s Cyber Security

Programme, the UNIMAN has introduced a 2-factor authentication, thus the access to data can be safe and secured.

Moreover, All the participants who consent to take part in the study performed by UNIMAN will be anticipated to finish the cancer assessment questionnaires and provide the blood sample unless they withdraw from this study.

Each respective data measure/variable from primary data for each participant will only be collected one time (while participants enter the study initially).

2.1.1.2 Data format and distribution

The REFLECT cancer assessment data will be the result of questionnaires and will be imported as a numerical value for each factor/variable. Data dictionary for this has already been provided to iHelp partners and is planned to be detailed in the context of D3.8 (“Standardisation and Quality Assurance of Heterogenous Data II”) that is planned to be delivered in M20. The genetic biomarkers will be the result of SNPs and we will import them as Polygenic Risk Score (PRS). All the data will be shared in CSV format and all the primary data variables are considered as important and mandatory for the final analysis.

UNIMAN will recruit 1500 healthy participants with the expectation of equal numbers of males and females and expect a third to have high genetic risk. The enrolled participants have to be free of cancer when joining the study and the age has to be between 45-70 years old.

During the implementation of the studies, UNIMAN will have a regular review process to monitor whether the distribution is balanced.

2.1.1.3 Data ingestion process and methodology

In terms of preliminary data processing, no processing will be performed a priori for the data derived from risk assessment. For genetic data, UNIMAN will process all raw genetic data for data Quality Check, QC (SNPs QC and sample QC) and also compute individual polygenic score. The Polygenic score will be then shared with other partners.

The generated data will be only offline and only on premise available.

After the primary data will be captured, UNIMAN will ensure that data from each participant will be anonymized and without traceable identification, and then the anonymized results will be shared with iHelp partners by connecting to the iHelp platform through the APIs provided by the technical partners. The established dictionary and the anonymized results will be then accessed through the API.

Both the cancer assessment from REFLECT and genetic biomarkers data will be expected to be ingested once a month or once every 2 months depending on how fast the results on genetic markers will be obtained, followed by the time for the data process mechanism.

Considering timelines and delays, an estimated delay of no later than 1 month could be caused by the processing of genetic markers as this relies on a commercial company and their specific time slot for running the samples.

2.1.2 Pilot #2 – FPG

2.1.2.1 Data collection strategy and details

Data for risk assessment will be generated by our infrastructure based on the risk assessment criteria for example participants with no history of cancer and of age between 40-75. The data collection effort is split in three distinct pipelines, based on the origin of the data:

- Data originating from the hospital infrastructure. The primary infrastructure is composed of two main parts: the Data Warehouse/data lake layer and the data marts layer. The first layer, within the protected space of the ICT (Information and Communications Technology) department, is characterized by the collection of longitudinal clinical data by producing specific views (such as information on admissions, reports on various clinical areas, information on laboratory analyses, etc.), that are essentially replicas of the archives that are filled daily in the course of clinical practice. The diverse variety of data sources is used as input of the second part of the infrastructure, responsible for data qualification, validation, quality check and creation of thematic data marts filled with the data defined in the iHelp ontology. In FPG's perspective, a data mart is a complete representation of the available data for the pilot. This DataMart is then enriched with the data stemming from the following two points.
- Data originating from apps. Questionnaire data is extracted from the app APIs, processed through the second layer of the previous hospital infrastructure, and then added to the existing DataMart.
- Data originating from the doctors. Some data cannot be extracted from the hospital infrastructure, and as such, a specific standardized data collection application has been provided to the doctors, in order to facilitate data collection. The results of the standardized data collection are added to the DataMart.

While FPG considers all variables as mandatory and expect full compliance by the patients; the technical partners will have to determine which variables will be the most important for the predictive models they will be developing.

Data will be automatically collected when available based on the nature of the variable (e.g., once at enrollment, when the result of a specific blood test is available, and so on).

2.1.2.2 Data format and distribution

Considering data structure, the specific pilot datasets and provided data schema have already been introduced to the technical partners and detailed in D3.7 ("Standardisation and Quality Assurance of Heterogenous Data I"), D3.1 ("Data Modelling and Integrated Health Records: Design and open specification I") and D2.1 ("State of the art and requirements analysis I"). As far as prospective data is concerned, this Pilot is an observational study and it does not have required data distributions and will recruit any patient in line with the inclusion criteria, as detailed in D6.1 ("Coordination of pilot scenarios for personalized healthcare – early risk identification, prevention and intervention measures I").

The retrospective data has the distributions according to Table 1 and Table 2.

Moreover, the total number of patients count with pancreatic cancer and radiotherapy were 116.

Table 1: Retrospective data results

Distribution factors	Count	Percentages (%)
Males	58	50
Median age	67	IQR 59.5 – 71.0
Had surgery	111	95.69
Had Chemotherapy	104	89.66

Table 2: Radiotherapy timing

Distribution factors	Count	Percentages (%)
RT sandwich	58	50
After chemo	38	32.76
only RT	12	10.34
Before chemo	8	6.9

The analysis of data bias should be provided by the technical partners working on the data that the FPG pilot provides, based on the needs and characteristics of the predictive models that will be developed. No specific biases are expected from FPG's perspective.

As FPG pilot recruits all patients in line with the inclusion criteria and do not expect any specific data bias, the recruitment process will be regularly monitored without preconceived strategies. FPG pilot will react to the distributions at hand if necessary.

2.1.2.3 Data ingestion process and methodology

Adherence to the created ontology will be strictly enforced during data processing and before adding the data to the DataMart. This includes both conformance checks and any modifications to the data in order to fit the ontology (e.g., joining data entries representing specific subgroups into one unified main group).

After data capture, the data will be stored on an iHelp specific machine in the FPG data storage facility. As previously said, the data cannot leave the FPG premise, as such, any analysis will be conducted on the local iHelp machine through the docker infrastructure, and the results will be sent to the iHelp platform.

Only FPG staff and researchers on FPG premises will have access to the acquired data. Due to the high protection level required by the clinical facility, data can only be accessed through the iHelp docker infrastructure. Timewise, data will be ingested into the main DataMart at scheduled intervals. At the moment this interval is set to weekly ingestions. This interval can be easily modified based on the ongoing needs.

FPG's infrastructure is connected to the hospitals' main databases, as such, the periodic ingestion procedures (currently set to weekly captures) offer access to all available data from the moment the entries appear in the hospitals' database. The time delay between the moment when a test is done and when the data becomes available, while usually very short, is unfortunately dependent on the specific variable and the time it takes to validate the data (e.g., the time it takes to analyse and validate a blood sample) and is hard to be influenced, aiming a faster process. Once captured, the data becomes visible to the local iHelp

infrastructure in less than two hours. FPG does not upload data outside of the hospitals' premise, thus there is no time requirement or time expectation with regards to platform data ingestion delays.

2.1.3 Pilot #3 – HDM

2.1.3.1 Data collection strategy and details

HDM pilot is now focused in predicting the risk of suffering Pancreatic Cancer (PC), but in the effect of changing life habits over risk factors, that will be measured at epigenomic level through the measurement of methylation indexes.

This pilot will obtain an initial extraction of the patients' medical records that are present in Electrical Medical Records (EMRs). The extraction will be performed in CSV files and following the OMOP data format (Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership), that is an EU standard defined in the EHDEN EU project (<https://www.ehden.eu/>) and can be easily transformed to FHIR format before ingestion in iHelp.

In this pilot, the lab analytical results are the most important, as they will be the base to perform the epigenomic changes measurements at the end of the pilot.

After the initial EMR ingestion, results of blood tests will be ingested by iHelp each three months.

2.1.3.2 Data format and distribution

HDM's primary data will be offered to iHelp in OMOP format. The only modification to this EU standard format has been the addition of two columns to each table, that maps a different object. Those two columns will be used to describe codified values: one column will describe the vocabulary used and the other the codified value inside that dictionary.

As compared to the initial planning, the only change has been the addition of the two columns mentioned above, for the codified values.

Patients will be separated into two main groups:

- Patients directly inside the program:
 - 4 patients with cancer. They only will provide their medical record and one single blood sample to perform epigenomic analytics.
 - 14 patients without pancreatic cancer. In addition to the medical record, a blood sample will be provided each 3 months.
- Patients not directly inside the program:
 - An extraction from around 100K patients will be anonymized and sent to iHelp.

In HDM pilot there are not biases inside the data. The 100K patients represent the full population of the geographic area that is assigned to the hospital. If any bias should appear, is not linked with the pilot but with the population itself.

The study groups comparisons will be conducted differentiating two groups: diagnosed vs undiagnosed.

2.1.3.3 Data ingestion process and methodology

The primary data that will be shared with iHelp will be extracted from the Electronic Medical Record (EMR) in place at HDM. That EMR is implemented by ORACLE's CERNER MILLENNIUM, which is one of the top 3

EMR systems in the marketplace, and that introduces many controls before allowing the data to be persisted (stored), whose details are not accessible to external stakeholders and cannot therefore be detailed.

This pilot will share the primary data with iHelp partners by connecting to the iHelp platform through the API. The data from patients directly involved in the project will be sent as it is to the iHelp platform, where it will be joined with the secondary data. For the patients that are not directly involved in the study, and whose data will be used to train the AI models, HDM will anonymize it before sending it to the iHelp platform.

In the HDM pilot no real-time ingestion of primary data is needed. Primary data will be sent once at the beginning of the pilot and then each three months a new sending will be performed, to allow monitoring the patients that participate in the study.

Once ingested through the API to the iHelp platform, the data can be accessed utilizing the established dictionary and the offered results.

During the pilot new primary data consisting of lab results will be gathered and sent to the iHelp platform. From the acquisition of the data within HDM premises until the data will be sent to the iHelp platform, the maximum delay time will be seven days.

2.1.4 Pilot #4 – MUP

2.1.4.1 Data collection strategy and details

A sample data for risk assessment has already been provided, above 900 cases, with dictionary and description that will be detailed in D3.8 (“Standardisation and Quality Assurance of Heterogenous Data II”).

The data that has been collected so far is the retrospective data for patients already diagnosed with Pancreatic Cancer (PC) and control group patients that were examined by medical specialists for complains related to other causes than PC diseases. The data was acquired via the medical reports of the Oncology center, Medical Centre, and Hospital archives.

Within the pilot MUP, the medical specialists will be addressed with a focused questionnaire to survey their awareness regarding the early symptoms and tests that could allow triage of the patients with risk of development of PC and the capabilities of the information communication technologies (ICT) to support the health risk assessment and medical decision on prevention, treatment, and monitoring. The survey will be conducted as a face to face and digital (distant, remote) interview. The data will be analyzed and stored into the premises of MUP as an Excel table format.

All the data planned to be collected for the pilot is with equal importance; therefore, all variables will be mandatory, and no missing data is to be expected.

Regarding data collection frequency, it is required at least five to six months period between the first and the second survey, so that the medical professionals have a clear vision regarding the benefits of the platform based on the monitoring of their patients.

2.1.4.2 Data format and distribution

No data related to the medical specialists' awareness is provided so far. The questionnaire is under development.

MUP has provided so far retrospective data of above 300 patients with PC and above 600 patients for the control group, but this data is not related to the Pilot #4. The plan is to engage at least 150-200 medical professionals from different specialties in order to achieve a statistical value of our assessment. It will be beneficial if 100 patients from the risky groups could be included for assessment of the platform implementation. The plan is to have equal number male and female from the highly risk age groups.

The MUP team is performing an aggressive face to face campaign within the medical community in order to engage medical specialists as much as possible to participate into the pilot.

2.1.4.3 Data ingestion process and methodology

The plan is to collect all the data on premises and to insert only the outcome into the platform. The data that will be collected from the patients of the medical specialists interested to participate in the study, will be on premises, because it will serve the medics to evaluate the created iHelp platform utility and usability for the clinical practice.

All the data will be stored at dedicated MUP server, and the connection with the main iHelp infrastructures has already been discussed and agreed in collaboration with the technical experts. The Real-World Data (RWD) will be inserted at a later stage and the outcomes of the analysis will be available after the final processing by the internal iHelp components.

2.1.5 Pilot #5 – TMU

2.1.5.1 Data collection strategy and details

The primary data will be used to identify high-risk patients (Pancreatic and Liver). In order to create individual risk measures, analysts will examine the electronic health records (EHRs) of TMU's patients. Age, sex, diagnostic codes, blood test results, medication information, comorbidities, and family history are all included the EHR data.

The pilot's primary data (retrospective data) will be collected from the TMU Clinical Data Repository (TMU-CDR) database, and thereafter AI-based data analytics models will be developed to identify people at high risk of developing pancreatic and liver cancer.

In this phase of risk prediction, the required variables for AI based big data analytics would be considered from the available TMU-CDR database. These variables include clinical visits, diagnoses, and medications in this study along with the records of pancreatic and liver cancer diagnostic tests and comorbidities.

The medical records of patients will be downloaded from the TMU-CDR database and stored on a secure storage on the university's network.

The vocabulary and code corresponding to the coded values are work in progress and will be provided to the technical partners in a month time.

Some mandatory variables are crucial for risk prediction, as well as linking variables to other datasets within the database. Any updates made in the future will be shared as well.

If the data contains missing values, they must be imputed or eliminated before the data can be further analyzed.

The primary data (retrospective data) for each participant will only be collected one time from the TMU-CDR database as described in D2.1 (“State of the art and requirements analysis I”).

2.1.5.2 Data format and distribution

TMU’s data is available in SAS format (Statistical Analysis System). In terms of data distribution, a precise number of people who have liver or pancreatic cancer cannot yet be determined. The exact distribution will be clear once TMU receive the ethical approval and the final data. Although, there are 196 individuals with Pancreatic Cancer (56.6 percent males) and about 4,040 patients with liver cancer overall (72.2% men) in the database.

The distribution of classes in the TMU’s dataset may not be uniform, therefore this imbalance needs to be treated accordingly by the technical partners when developing the AI-based prediction models.

For instance, males versus females, cancer (liver and pancreatic) versus non-cancer, etc. This can be overcome by using machine learning techniques like resampling the training set (under-sampling, over-sampling, generating synthetic data (SMOTE - Synthetic Minority oversampling TEchnique), or re-sampling with different ratios between the uneven datasets), trying different machine learning algorithms and choosing different evaluation metrics like sensitivity, precision, AUROC (area under the receiver operating characteristics) etc.

During study groups (control vs experimental), the comparisons will be conducted differentiating two groups: diagnosed (cancer- liver and pancreatic) vs undiagnosed (non-cancer). No strategy will be followed to overcome biases in the data capturing process.

Machine learning tools will be used by technical partners to overcome distribution issues.

2.1.5.3 Data ingestion process and methodology

After the capture of primary data, it will be stored in the TMU’s data storage facility. The primary data cannot leave Taiwan. But partners can access the analysis' results (AI-based analytical results) remotely via a server located on TMU's premises. Only TMU staff and researchers on the premises will have access to the acquired data.

The results of primary data analysis can be accessed via remote access to our server (located at TMU).

Data sample has already been shared with all the members of the consortium and the template provided was introduced in D3.7 (“Standardisation and Quality Assurance of Heterogenous Data I”). If needed, more sample data can be provided to the technical partners.

2.2 Secondary data

The secondary data refers to data collected from a trial of selected patients and usually comes from mobile applications, wearables, IoT devices, feedback questionnaires.

2.2.1 Pilot #1 – UNIMAN

2.2.1.1 Data collection details

The secondary data includes data derived from questionnaire in the three domains (psychological, social and quality of life information) and the epigenetic biomarker data. The three domains' questionnaires survey will be collected from the iHelp platform (Healthentia APP). The epigenetic data will be collected from consented participants' blood samples.

2.2.1.2 Data format and distribution

The three domains of questionnaires survey data will be the result of each questionnaire. UNIMAN will consider the before result data (before entering the prevention group) as the baseline and then compare the baseline data with the after-result data (6 months after entering the prevention group). Data format will be in CSV. Each questionnaire will be coded as in the data dictionary provided to iHelp relevant partners, which is to be introduced and detailed in the context of D3.8 ("Standardisation and Quality Assurance of Heterogenous Data II"), plan to be submitted on M20.

The epigenetic biomarkers will be the result of each methylation (CpG island) and UNIMAN will import them as PhenoAge (biological age). There were no baseline values, limits, or limitations. All the epigenetic biomarkers data will be likewise shared in CSV format.

As comparing with primary data, the same participants who have above-average cancer risk and signed the informed consented will have the primary and secondary data recorded.

2.2.1.3 Data ingestion process and methodology

Both three domains' questionnaires survey will be ingested at month one of recruitment and then month 6. For epigenetic age, UNIMAN also plans to ingest data from beginning and then at the end of the 6-month period.

2.2.2 Pilot #2 – FPG

2.2.2.1 Data collection details

As with the primary data, the data collection effort is split in three distinct pipelines, based on the expected origin of the data.

- Data originating from the hospital infrastructure. The primary infrastructure is composed of two main parts: the Data Warehouse/data lake layer and the data marts layer. The first layer, within the protected space of FPG's ICT (Information and Communications Technology) department, is characterized by the collection of longitudinal clinical data by producing specific views (such as information on admissions, reports on various clinical areas, information on laboratory analyses, etc.) that are essentially replicas of the archives that are filled daily in the course of clinical practice. The diverse variety of data sources is used as input of the second part of the infrastructure, responsible for data qualification, validation, quality check and creation of thematic data marts filled with the data defined in the iHelp ontology. A data mart is a complete representation of the available data for the pilot. This DataMart is then enriched with the data stemming from the following two points.

- Data originating from apps. Questionnaire data is extracted from the app APIs, processed through the second layer of the previous hospital infrastructure, and then added to the existing DataMart.
- Data originating from the doctors. Some data cannot be extracted from the hospital infrastructure, and as such, a specific standardized data collection application has been provided to the doctors, in order to facilitate data collection. The results of the standardized data collection are added to the DataMart.

2.2.2.2 Data format and distribution

Specific descriptions and information concerning the pilot datasets have already been shared with the technical partners in deliverables D2.1 (“State of the art and requirements analysis I”) and D2.2 (“State of the art and requirements analysis II”). Additional details will have to be provided by the secondary data providers, as FPG has no sample data for prospective secondary data right now.

Regarding the primary and secondary data connection, where possible and relevant, the same patients will have primary and secondary data recorded.

2.2.2.3 Data ingestion process and methodology

Data will be ingested into the main DataMart at scheduled intervals. At the moment, this interval is set to weekly ingestions. This interval can be adjusted easily based on the recurrent needs.

2.2.3 Pilot #3 – HDM

2.2.3.1 Data collection details

HDM pilot’s secondary data will be only collected for the 14 patients without P.C. (see previous Section 2.1.3.1). Those patients will receive a wearable device (GARMIN VIVOSMART 4) to automatically collect some vital signs regarding general status and also sleep quality and physical activity. In addition to this, some questionnaires have been defined inside the Healthentia APP to complete data of interest for the study. Mainly weight and height, and four questionnaires:

- FTND (Fagerstrom TEST for Nicotine Dependence): to evaluate nicotine dependence level
- AUDIT (Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test): to evaluate alcohol consumption
- PSS (Perceived Stress Scale): to evaluate the perceives stress level
- DIET: to evaluate the alimentary behaviors. Instead of using a questionnaire as was initially proposed for evaluating the diet, a nutrition widget provided by the Healthentia mobile APP will be used instead.

2.2.3.2 Data format and distribution

Regarding the tests, no data type will be entered, patients will just select one option among a set of options. The result of the test will be calculated by the Healthentia APP.

Referring to the connection to primary data patient’s distribution, distinct patients will have secondary data recorded, as follows:

- For patients directly inside the program:
 - 4 patients with cancer. Only primary data.
 - 14 patients without pancreatic cancer. Both primary and secondary data.
- For patients not directly inside the program:

- Only primary data.

2.2.3.3 Data ingestion process and methodology

The tests will be requested weekly to the patients through the Healthentia APP. Regarding the data acquired by the wearable, it will be continuous along the duration of the pilot.

2.2.4 Pilot #4 – MUP

2.2.4.1 Data collection details

The data will be collected as face to face or by digital remote interview. MUP will provide to the interested medical specialists wearable devices (Garmin bracelets) for collection of the patient secondary data. Data collection: acquiring the data from devices (mobile & wearable).

2.2.4.2 Data format and distribution

The data structure will depend on the risk predict that has to be created, and the same patients will have primary and also secondary data collected.

2.2.4.3 Data ingestion process and methodology

The medical specialists plan is to receive and evaluate the patient's data on a weekly manner or when a dramatic change into the monitored variables occurs.

2.2.5 Pilot #5 – TMU

2.2.5.1 Data collection details

For digital intervention, the objective is to provide evidence that shows how digital interventions can enhance people's quality of life. The mobile app will collect basic user details, personal history, family history, habits, subjective sleep assessment, quality of life and symptoms. During follow-ups (every 2 months) at 2, 4 and 6 months, the patients' quality of life will be assessed using European Organization for the Research and Treatment of Cancer QLQ-C30 (EORTC QLQ-C30) questionnaire.

The mobile app will capture patient-reported outcomes (PROS) related to cancer symptoms, facilitating subjective data collection using Edmonton Symptom Assessment System (ESAS) questionnaire (daily or at least once a week). Sleep quality will be assessed using Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), with recurrency of once per month. All the data will be shared in CSV format.

Comparing with primary data, distinct patients will have secondary data collected. The first phase of our pilot focuses on identifying high-risk patients using machine learning methods, while the second phase is concerned with patients who have already been diagnosed with cancer and will get digital interventions.

2.2.5.2 Data ingestion process and methodology

Earlier the aim of TMU's study was to predict high risk individuals towards pancreatic & liver cancer for early-stage management of the disease and further explore the effect of digital therapeutics solutions among these individuals.

The present goal is to create risk prediction models and analyse interventions that can help cancer patients engage and motivate them to enhance their quality of life. For our digital intervention (second phase of the

study), TMU is now focused on patients who have already been diagnosed with cancer rather than those who are at high risk of developing cancer.

This pilot's contribution is divided into 2 separate phases:

- Phase 1: To exploit the TMU Clinical Data Repository (TMU-CDR) database and utilize AI-based data analytics models, to determine individuals with a high risk to develop pancreatic & liver cancer (for early-stage management of the disease).
- Phase 2: To conduct a digital trial, an observational study, using mobile applications for personalized healthcare and improved quality of life, among the liver and pancreatic cancer patients.

Through the Healthentia APP, patients will be asked to complete surveys- weekly (ESAS questionnaire), monthly (PSQI), or bi-monthly (EORTC). After TMU will acquire wearables, then the frequency to acquire the data provided by the wearable can be discussed with Innovation Sprint.

3 Evaluation instruments for data collection

Evaluation instruments and procedures before, during or after the execution of the experimental studies for data collection or data gathered from other sources (e.g., databases, shared or merged data from other partners) will be described in this section.

Pilots will give details about how the data collection will be evaluated by measuring the quantity and the quality of this process. Also, one aspect that will be described by pilots is how the data flow will be managed.

3.1 Pilot #1 – UNIMAN

For the blood samples, quality control will be performed, and the labels will be checked to match the digital ID of each participant. For all the questionnaires, UNIMAN will check the label match the digital ID and ensure the response rate. The participants who have many missing questions answered will be closely followed up.

By controlling through mechanisms such as reviewing the data, UNIMAN intends to maintain the same quantity of delivered data during the development of the project.

UNIMAN will regularly perform quality control and resolve the problems that might appear as it already has a study protocol in place, and it will be followed strictly.

3.2 Pilot #2 – FPG

FPG's infrastructure creates daily data summaries from which the data collection process and progress can be analysed, including data quality and quantity by analysing the number of missing data entries and by extracting descriptive statistics.

Quality controls will be regularly performed, and any problems occurred will be resolved. FPG will adhere to the study protocol approved by the FPG internal ethics committee.

3.3 Pilot #3 – HDM

As explained in the section regarding primary data, the EMR software in use at HDM ensures the data quality, introducing rules and controls that apply to the incoming data before it can be persisted. That ensures the data extracted and sent to iHelp is quality assured.

HMD's data collection will be regularly reviewed both in process and quantity.

Once the ingestion procedures will be explained, controls will be set up to monitor the data flow behaves as expected.

3.4 Pilot #4 – MUP

All the data used by the medics for their assessment has to be in accordance with the requirements set by the risk predictor. MUP plans to reach the above-mentioned numbers of medical specialists involved to fit the planned requirements.

By constant and frequent connection between the MUP team and the participating medical specialists MUP intends to manage the dataflow efficiently.

3.5 Pilot #5 – TMU

Primary data quality evaluation metrics will be checked. Among the different data metrics, the most essential characteristic of any data is completeness of data, relevance of data, uniformity of data, biases, labelling, and data relations.

For all the questionnaires, TMU will ensure the response rate for secondary data. The participants who have many missing questions answered will be closely followed up.

TMU will assess the data collection process and quantity on a regular basis.

Quality control will be performed on a regular basis and any issues that arise to control the data flow will be addressed.

4 Pilot evaluation/assessment measures

To better standardize the measurement of each pilot's contribution in terms of data provisioning, a series of tools have been defined and described in this section. The assessment is defined using concepts like success outcome, evaluation measures definition or qualitative tools such as feedback, questionnaires, in-depth interviews.

As a general note, regularly random checks for secondary data will be performed by each partner in order to test the data quality during the implementation of the project.

4.1 Pilot #1 – UNIMAN

Taking note that there are two types of data primary and secondary, the success outcome will be measured using the following strategies.

The participants successfully complete the online cancer risk assessment and data generated through the UNIMAN platform. The data can then be ingested to iHelp platform. Genetic score derives for everyone.

The participants will successfully complete three domains' assessments (psychological, social, and quality of life information) and also epigenetic age can be calculated for each individual.

The number of completed questionnaires and blood samples that can be processed and scored are the measurements that will help to define the success of the data acquirement.

The primary data evaluation will be measured through regular review.

The questionnaires on the UoM cancer assessment REFLECT website will be assessed while participants enter our study initially. UNIMAN will extract DNA from the blood sample and then analyze the SNPs in order to calculate the PRS (score).

The secondary type of data will be measured also through regular review.

The questionnaires on the iHelp package will be assessed before and 6 months after the participants join this preventive study. The DNA will be extracted from the blood sample and then the DNA will be analyzed to evaluate the biological age.

All the recruitment processes including the number of participants and the response rate will be monitored by the real-time data transferred to our excel.

4.2 Pilot #2 – FPG

The success definition will be set by the following items:

- High degree of patient compliance within the study.
- Positive patient feedback on the study and any interactions with the medical staff.
- Development of a toxicity-related predictive model.

The evaluation measures will be defined by the following items:

- Patient compliance will be evaluated through the analysis of the quantity and quality of the available data and through the results of the available questionnaires and feedback provided by the patient.

- Patient feedback will be evaluated through specific questionnaires and any other feedback the patients is interested in giving.
- The evaluation of the predictive model will be in the hands of the technical partners developing the models and will be based on the specific characteristics of the models.

Any evaluation (except the evaluation of the predictive model) will be conducted based on the data stemming from FPG data collection efforts and the data generated by FPG's infrastructure. Specific care will be taking in evaluation any available results through relevant statistical computations.

The infrastructure creates daily data summaries from which the recruitment process can be analysed.

4.3 Pilot #3 – HDM

To ensure success, the records extracted from HDM's EMR for the participants, will include data for all the OMOP resources included in the primary data definition. The data can then be ingested to the iHelp platform.

With regards to secondary data, the participants will successfully complete the provided forms included in the Healthentia APP with the requested periodicity. Data from the wearable device is received periodically.

An epigenomic signature related with the smoking will be measured at the beginning and at the end of the pilot, for the patients directly involved in the pilot. With that, the effect of quitting smoking will be evidenced at epigenomic level, what could offer evidence of the risk reduction of PC since methylation is agreed as previous step to mutation, that is directly related with cancer in general, and P.C. in particular.

The evaluation measures will be conducted accordingly:

- Primary data: Initial download of electronic medical record of patients, plus new lab results each three months, coming from blood samples that will be taken on the same periodicity.
- Secondary data: questionnaires regarding alcohol ingestion, nicotine dependency, physical activity, quality of sleep and eating patterns will be provided weekly. By this, the change of life habits could be evaluated, what will be of interest to identify if the level of methylation changes is aligned to those changes in life habits.

The recruitment process is vital in HDM pilot since it will focus on measuring changes in epigenomic markers associated with smoking, and therefore it will ensure that patients involved in the process, will quit smoking. For that reason, patients directly involved are at the same time hospital staff that have participated in direct interviews and ensured their intention to quit smoking. Surrounding the study activities, HDM will offer a set of additional benefits to help to ensure the success, like yoga classes or personalized diet consultancy.

The recruitment process did start eight weeks ago and have been monitored by the main investigators of the HDM pilot.

4.4 Pilot #4 – MUP

The success outcome is re-assured by the fact that enough medics from the preliminary defined medical specialties (oncology, general and abdomen surgery, gastroenterology, endocrinology, internal medicine, and family medicine) to be interested and included into the pilot.

Secondary aspect is these medics to include sufficient patients to monitor for assessing the value of the iHelp implementation define main and secondary aspects for a successful outcome.

The main evaluation measure is the balance of the medics' participation into the project from pre-hospital and hospital systems. Focus must be on involving more family and internal medicine specialists as they are at the first line of healthcare and are of utmost importance for the early diagnose and triage of the patients at risk.

4.5 Pilot #5 – TMU

The items below define main and secondary aspects for a successful outcome:

1. Phase 1:
 - Successful access to the TMU-CDR database.
 - AI-based model successfully predicts high risk liver and pancreatic cancer patients.
 - Results of the analysis can then be ingested to the iHelp platform.

2. Phase 2:
 - Participants successfully completes questionnaires.
 - Mobile app successfully delivers personalized recommendations/decision-support.
 - TMU timely receives user feedback for the personalized motivational messages.
 - There is improvement in quality of life among cancer patients due to digital interventions.

The “digital solutions” user experiences will be evaluated: user engagement, usefulness of personalized information, impact of recommendations etc. will be performed based on the responses gathered through the same applications used in the digital trials.

The evaluation measures provided by TMU will be:

- Primary data:
 - Machine learning evaluation metrics will be used- Accuracy, Precision, Recall, AUC etc.
- Secondary data: Questionnaires through regular review.
 - Questionnaires: questionnaires on the iHelp package will be assessed at 2, 4 and 6 months.
 - User experience assessment of the Digital solutions:
 - Metrics from the app
 - Number of answered questions for the PRO and interactions towards the recommendations
 - Number of sessions¹, frequency of logins, mean time spent per session, number of performed activities, and number of questionnaires reported, number of rated motivational messages.

TMU will monitor all the recruitment processes including the number of participants and the response rate by the real-time data transferred to our excel.

¹ A session is defined as each time the user opens the app until it is closed

5 Risk assessment: possible risks, corrective actions and process

To ensure smooth execution of the pilots and address any risks that may jeopardize the success of the pilots, partners have identified potential risks that may occur during the pilot phase, as well as strategies to mitigate the negative impact of these risks.

Potential risks are monitored and managed through the entire project in T1.3 (“Quality and Risk Management”). In this respect, an update of the risk register will be conducted periodically, depending on the overall progress of the pilot’s process.

The risk methodology to be followed is based on the principle “risk is likelihood by impact”, while impact has three main pillars, namely time, quality, and relevance. The following mappings in Table 3 and Table 4 are considered for likelihood and mapping.

Table 3: Likelihood mapping

Likelihood	Percentage	Label
Low	Below 10%	1
Medium	10-40%	2
High	40-70%	3
Very high	70-100%	4

Table 4: Impact mapping

Impact	Label
No	0
Low	1
Medium	2
High	3
Critical	4

This section seeks to address three main questions:

- What are the possible risks for data collection, pilot evaluation and execution?
- How will the risk assessment be performed?
- What are the risks mitigation strategies?

5.1 Pilot #1 – UNIMAN

The possible risks for data collection, that UNIMAN foresee are:

- 1 Insufficient participants with above-average cancer risk.
- 2 Insufficient above-average cancer risk participants consent to attend our biomarker assessment study.
- 3 Insufficient above-average cancer risk participants consent to attend our prevention study.

There are two types of risks assessment that will be performed:

1. Quality assessment:

For all the questionnaires result, they will check the label to match the digital ID initially and then ensure the response rate. UNIMAN will closely follow up with those participants who have many missing questions answer.

For the blood sample, quality control will be performed and the label will be checked to match the digital ID of each participant.

2. Quantity assessment:

UNIMAN will ensure the number of recruiting participants, the number of participants with above-average cancer risk, the number of participants who consent to enter the biomarker assessment and the number of participants who consent to enter the preventive study meet our expectations.

UNIMAN will monitor the number of participants in recruitment, the number of participants who consent to enter the biomarker assessment and the number of participants who consent to enter the preventive study in time. If the above number does not meet the identified expectations, UNIMAN will hold more recruitment events. In addition, if the questionnaire response rate is low, UNIMAN will closely follow up with those participants who have many missing questions answer.

Table 5: UNIMAN risk description and mitigation actions.

Risk description	Impact description	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation actions
Insufficient participants with above-average cancer risk.	The number of participants to join our biomarker assessment and prevention group may be insufficiency	Low	Low	Ensuring the number of participants in recruitment sufficiency.
Insufficient above-average cancer risk participants consent to attend our biomarker assessment study.	The blood sample may be insufficiency	Low	Low	Ensuring the above-average cancer risk participants who consent to attend our biomarker assessment study sufficiently. Otherwise, UNIMAN will hold more events to recruit participants.
Insufficient above-average cancer risk participants consent to attend our prevention study	The participants who like to join our prevention group may be insufficient	Low	Low	UNIMAN will ensure that above-average cancer risk participants who consent to attend our prevention group study are sufficient. Otherwise, UNIMAN will hold more events to recruit participants.

Questionnaires response rate low	The result of the questionnaire survey will have a bias	Low	Low	If the questionnaire response rate is low, UNIMAN will closely follow up with those participants who have many missing questions answer.
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5.2 Pilot #2 – FPG

The possible risks for data collection, in our vision, are:

- Insufficient patient compliance.
- Technical issues with wearables.
- Technical issues with our infrastructure.
- Low number of recruited patients.

FPG's infrastructure provides regular updates on the available data, as such regular assessments can provide an overview of both the quality and quantity of the available data, and measure the current risk (e.g., no data coming from wearables, no newly recruited patients, no data from infrastructure).

FPG will start a patient-sensibilization campaign during recruitment in order to keep compliance as high as possible. FPG will work with secondary data providers and wearable providers in order to keep any issues from arising or resolving them in an efficient manner. The infrastructure is well maintained, and ample backups of the data will be generated. FPG will start a recruitment campaign in order to recruit as many patients as possible.

Table 6: FPG risk description and mitigation actions

Risk description	Impact description	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation actions
Insufficient patient compliance.	Lower data quality.	Low	Low	FPG will start a patient-sensibilization campaign during recruitment in order to keep compliance as high as possible.
Technical issues with wearables.	No secondary data will be available.	Low	Low	FPG will work with secondary data providers and wearable providers in order to keep any issues from arising or resolving them in an efficient manner.
Technical issues with our infrastructure.	No data available.	Low	Critical	FPG infrastructure is well maintained, and ample backups of the data will be generated.
Low number of recruited patients.	Less leeway in developing predictive models.	Low	Medium	FPG will start a recruitment campaign in order to recruit as

				many patients as possible.
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5.3 Pilot #3 – HDM

The possible risk for data collection is that insufficient participants that agreed to quit smoking will finally achieve it during the study.

The quality assessment will be achieved by monitoring the secondary data provided from the participants to ensure there are not many outliers. By continuously monitoring, it will be ensured that the responses provided by the participants are aligned with the periodicity expected to ensure there will be enough data to perform the study.

The main mitigation strategy has been taking during the pilot's design, since HDM investigators chose to include hospital staff as patients under study to maximize adherence to the study, availability to reach the subjects in case any deviation may be found, and fluent communication during the pilot execution.

Table 7: HDM risk description and mitigation actions

Risk description	Impact description	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation actions
Insufficient participants achieve quitting smoking.	Array to analyse change in methylation indexed can not be filled.	Low	High	Choose hospital staff as subjects under study. Select more patients than needed to allow some margin of "error".

5.4 Pilot #4 – MUP

The main risk that MUP has identified is the insufficient number of medical specialists interested into participation. This will reflect on the number of patients included into monitoring and the assessment process. The likelihood of these risks to happen is high (3) and the impact is critical (4).

Into the process of collecting the retrospective data MUP team has faced extremely high level of reluctance from the medical specialists to share any data for the project development. Also, a lack of interest was manifested by general practitioners and general surgeons, which unfortunately are the main target groups. The data was collected by extremely limited sources.

The mitigation strategy consists of organizing discussions, workshops and participating at conferences regarding the capabilities and significance of the ICT into the process of PC patients at risk early triage and prevention, treatment, and monitoring.

Table 8: MUP risk description and mitigation actions

Risk description	Impact description	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation actions
Insufficient number of medical	The low number of participating medical	High	Critical	Organizing discussions, workshops and

specialists interested into participation	specialists will not allow the pilot to achieve representative sample for the measurement of iHelp impact on medical specialists' awareness regarding the early diagnosis of the PC			participating at conferences regarding the capabilities and significance of the ICT into the process of PC patients at risk early triage and prevention, treatment, and monitoring.
Insufficient number of patients interested into participation	The low number of participating medical specialists will not allow sufficient patients to be included into the platform testing that could lead to insufficiency of data for the clinicians to make their evaluation.	High	Critical	Organizing discussions, workshops and participating at conferences regarding the capabilities and significance of the ICT into the process of PC patients at risk early triage and prevention, treatment, and monitoring.

5.5 Pilot #5 – TMU

The potential risks that could appear during the data handling process are listed below.

- Insufficient participants during digital intervention.
- Technical issues with wearables.
- Questionnaires response rate low

These risks will be mitigated by closely follow up with those participants who have many missing questions answer. Also, TMU will ensure the number of recruiting participants who consent to enter the digital intervention.

Table 9: TMU risk description and mitigation actions

Risk description	Impact description	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation actions
Insufficient participants for digital intervention	If number of participants (n=50) does not meet our expectations for digital intervention, then it will affect the quality of results.	Low	Low	Collaboration with oncology team comprising of physicians and nurses at TMU hospital. Finding ways to better advertise and communicate the study goals.
Technical issues with wearables	Can lead to loss of secondary data	Medium	Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Criterion to be pre-defined: "valid days" and "numbers of valid days according to previous literature. ▪ Daily summary data can be derived. ▪ Robust data processing and feature engineering.

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Random checks during data collection in case there are issues with synchronization of wearables with the app.
Questionnaires response rate low	The result of the questionnaire survey will have a bias	Low	Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ If the response rate to the questionnaire is poor, TMU will closely monitor those individuals who have numerous unanswered questions. ▪ Alerts can be triggered via Healthentia app so that users are reminded of their low response.

6 Conclusion and next steps

From the above explanations of pilot's assessments, this document aims to describe the initial strategy, potential risks in data collection and mitigation measures that will be applied within the remaining project's timeline to follow each pilot's development.

The next iteration of this deliverable, D6.6 ("Data Collection and Pilot Assessments II"), will be provided in M36 and will contain the specific details of the presented approach. The parts described in this current version will be updated and refined based of the findings that will be identified in the process of each pilot' implementation. The final pilot plans and use case scenarios will be elaborated, further evaluating outcomes of the iHelp approaches and solutions and the benefits they provide towards Pancreatic Cancer risk assessment.

In the next iteration of this deliverable, a set of conclusions in form of statistical measurements will be presented. These measurements will describe in which percentage, the actions specified by each pilot will be achieved by M36.

Moreover, a set of charts and tables will depict how the instruments, the risk assessments and the proposed measures will have improved the overall data collection and handling within the iHelp project.

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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ATC	Athens Technology Centre
AUDIT	Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test
CSV	Comma-Separated Value
D	Deliverable
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
EC	European Commission
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EMR	Electronical Medical Record
EORTC	European Organization for the Research and Treatment of Cancer
ESAS	Edmonton Symptom Assessment System
FPG	Agostino Gemelli University Policlinic
FTND	Fagerstrom Test for Nicotine Dependence
HDM	Hospital de Dénia-MarinaSalud
iSPRINT	Innovation Sprint
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IQR	Interquartile Range
LXS	LeanXcale
M	Month
MUP	Medical University Plovdiv
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PC	Pancreatic Cancer
PROS	patient-reported outcomes
PRS	Polygenic Risk Score
PSQI	Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index
PSS	Perceived Stress Scale
QC	Quality Check
REFLECT	Risk Estimation for Lifestyle Enhancement Combined Trial
RWD	Real-World Data
SAS	Statistical Analysis Software
SIE	Siemens
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Oversampling TEchnique
SPNPs	Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms Scaffold Protein Spinophilin
T	Task
TMU	Taipei Medical University
UNIMAN	University of Manchester
UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Centre

Terminology

CpG island	the " 5'—C—phosphate—G—3' " sequence of nucleotides, indicated on one DNA strand
Data mart	A data mart is a subject-oriented database that is often a partitioned segment of an enterprise data warehouse
FHIR	standard for health care data exchange, published by HL7 (https://www.hl7.org/fhir/)
REFLECT	Reflect is an online platform that contains a risk prediction calculator that offers users an idea of their personal future risk or chance of developing cancer. The website calculates cancer risk based on the answers provided to a lifestyle questionnaire. The answer to each individual question contributes to an overall risk in different ways (either increasing or decreasing the risk) and to different extents. This assessment is based on expert knowledge around these different factors.